

Recommendation for policy uptakes to foster urban circular bioeconomy across Europe

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What is HOOP? The pioneer HORIZON 2020 project that provided technical, regulatory and financial Project Development Assistance (PDA) to 8 European *Lighthouse* cities and regions to unlock urban circular bioeconomy (UCBE) projects.

HOOP in numbers

120+ M € of induced investments	94 Techno-environmental PDA actions	1600+ Stakeholders engaged
15+ Financial leverage	104 Financial and business models PDA actions	60+ Stakeholder events known as Biowaste Clubs
18 UCBE investment projects	27 Innovation public procurement PDA actions	2 Policy conferences
25 Technologies evaluated	3 Open market consultation processes	9 Study tours
50+ Reports & manuals elaborated		129 Members in the HOOP Network
7 UCBE evaluation tools produced		1 HOOP Circular Bioeconomy Hub
30 Webinars on UCBE		

Introduction

Over the course of four and a half years, the HOOP project was dedicated to empowering Lighthouse cities and regions to mobilize investments for the valorisation of biowaste into high value bioproducts. Technical partners meticulously optimized valorisation processes and conducted comprehensive assessments from environmental, technological, and regulatory standpoints. In parallel, they facilitated access to capital, developed tailored business models, and provided capacity-building support to public authorities engaged in innovation-oriented public procurement.

The HOOP Lighthouses and their project developers, faced different barriers and challenges for the implementation of circular bio-based solutions taking advantage of innovative biowaste and urban wastewater sludge technologies. These challenges were rigorously analysed to formulate targeted policy recommendations aimed at dismantling obstacles and fostering a more enabling environment for circular bioeconomy initiatives. Barriers mostly concern the

regulation (e.g. poorly adapted regulation for new circular biobased end-products, lack of harmonisation across Europe) and **economic aspects** (e.g. difficulty to find investment, unsustainable business models for bio-circular projects). Besides, testimonies from local players tended to show that barriers might also come from the **difficulty for public administration to interpret** specific regulations that can be regarded as highly technical, leading to a **very strict application**. This position paper aims at breaking down these barriers and proposing recommendations on how to overcome them.

This paper is the latest in a series of policy recommendation efforts by five Horizon 2020 projects focused on biowaste valorisation: [HOOP](#), [VALUEWASTE](#), [SCALIBUR](#), [WaysTUP!](#) and [CITYLOOPS](#). These projects piloted innovative methods to transform urban biowaste, such as food waste, green waste, and wastewater, into valuable products. Their collaboration began under the ROOTS initiative (circulaR pOlicies for changing the biOWasTe System), which from the outset called for increased funding to scale up biowaste recycling solutions,

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through R&D programmes like Horizon Europe and LIFE. ROOTS led to a 2022 [position paper](#), and now, following the closure of HOOP, this document presents an updated set of policy recommendations targeting specific EU and national regulatory frameworks.

Recommendations for promoting biowaste management

✓ **The introduction of mandatory recycling target for biowaste.** Even though it is now mandatory to separate biowaste, the lack of quantitative targets might limit the ambition of local collection schemes. The update of the Waste Framework Directive introduced targets of reduction of food waste, but no target on recycling of biowaste. Considering the different characteristics in the waste management system of each country and region observed in HOOP, targets might be set on Member State level or even at regional level. Targets should be tailored to the territorial context (such as tourism, option for in-situ biowaste management, etc.) but aligned with the common European target. When opting for regional targets, it must be ensured that the ambition of local authorities is not undermined by political convenience.

✓ **The introduction of financial support mechanisms and funds for new biowaste treatment plants.**

✓ **The promotion of economic instruments is essential to ensure the financial viability of ambitious biowaste management systems.** This involves penalising disposal, enhancing the economic attractiveness of recycling, and incentivising collection systems that achieve both high capture rates and high material quality. These measures have proven effective, as demonstrated by the experiences of the HOOP Lighthouses.

Recommendation for facilitating the material recovery of biowaste

✓ Establish criteria for the **End-of-Waste status for several types of urban biowaste (food waste, garden waste, etc.) to clarify and simplify the end-of-waste procedures.** The establishment of these criteria on European level by means of regulations, such as the ones established for metals or as the ones set in EU Fertiliser Products Regulation 2019/1009, would support the adoption of technologies for innovative valorisation, considering that procedures on Member State level or regional level become extremely long. The European Sustainable Phosphorous Platform suggests an end-of-waste evaluation protocol in their eNews no. 91 (Oct 2024).

✓ **When defining product specifications at regulatory level, create specific categories for products coming from biowaste,** with their own requirements, allowing for multiple re-uses, aligning with the principles of the circular economy.

✓ **The Revision of Invasive Alien Species Regulation 1143/2014 with regards to the use of the invasive species.** The current legislation forbids any kind of use for all species, without making any distinction between plants, animals and microorganisms. A mechanism such as the end point used in the Animal By-product Regulation (1069/2009), could be applied to establish treatment methods after which the biomass does not pose a hazard anymore. This would promote the valorisation over the destruction of certain vegetal species, transforming a problem into an opportunity.

Recommendations for specific bioproducts

✓ **The Revision of the regulations 767/2009 on the placing on the market and use of feed (Annex III Chapter 1.6) and 1069/2009.** This would allow the use of biowaste feedstock that either does not contain material of animal origin or meets the necessary requirements. The goal is to ensure that circular bioproducts (such as insect feed made from insects raised on plant-based biowaste) comply with all relevant technical, environmental, and safety standards. It also ensures that these products meet the criteria for management systems, including quality control, self-monitoring, and, where applicable, accreditation. The sorting of animal-free biowaste is successfully implemented in Bergen by the spinoff Ommat.

✓ **The revision of Regulation 1069/2009 (Article 5) to establish or permit the establishment of end-point criteria for the production of biochar intended for soil improvement.** This is supported by the fact that the pyrolysis operating temperatures required exceed significantly those set for other methods to achieve the end-of-waste status for animal by-products.

✓ **The Revision of Industrial Emission Directive 2010/75/EU with regards to the pyrolysis of biowaste of green waste to produce biochar.** This is to unlock the potential on the value-chain of biochar updating the regulatory framework to the repurpose of an old technology. Results on HOOP support the actual benefits of biochar application in pot and field tests. The enabling regulatory framework for the product does exist, but some barriers need to be addressed for the process. Especially: i) modify the definition of waste incineration, as this definition does not state clearly whether pyrolysis aimed at the obtention of biochar falls within its scope and ii) refine the categorisation of pyrolysis processes by distinguishing

pyrolysis of biomass (e.g., biowaste) from pyrolysis of fossil-based waste (e.g., plastics). Separate criteria should apply to biowaste pyrolysis for biochar production, given its distinct purpose and product.

✓ **Establish a regulatory framework for biotechnology products where biowaste is used in the production process.** Many of the innovative technologies for the treatment of biowaste are based on biotechnological processes. There is a complete lack of regulatory framework to address elements such as the growth media or the bioproducts obtained, while facing the challenges of other regulatory frameworks of the targeted market sectors. This creates uncertainty and becomes a risk that hinders investments. As an example, there is no framework for growth media produced with biowaste and it is not even considered in several regulations.

Recommendations to foster innovation

✓ **Promote the innovation public procurement with increase in funding schemes.** This is a primary need, as pre-commercial procurement (PCP) and public procurement of innovative solutions (PPI) are instruments for the cities and regions to solve their actual challenges, while pulling innovation while addressing specific needs. These funding mechanisms are critical for enabling cities and regions to adopt novel technologies while simultaneously stimulating market innovation.

✓ **Consider flexibility in the application of EU Taxonomy.** The Environmental Delegated Regulation 2023/2486 established the Technical Screening Criteria for the substantial contribution of activities to the Transition to the Circular Economy objective. These criteria are based on a list of contributing activities. Flexibility should be applied if there are activities having good or better environmental, societal and governance (ESG) performance than those listed in the delegated regulation for waste and wastewater management. This would facilitate the access of innovative sustainable technologies to green financing.

Recommendation for the enforcement of the EU regulation

✓ **Support Member States and their administrations** to take advantage of the possibilities offered by the different regulations (such as the definition

of alternative methods for the endpoint of ABP status) to ease the compliance with the regulation for recycling units. This could be done through expert technical or financial support to promoters/developers to undergo the safety assessment procedure by EFSA, as many tests are required. Communication and collaboration with DG SANTE and EFSA need to be promoted as they are key stakeholders in unlocking the innovative circular valorisation technologies.

✓ **Promote the implementation of product and process quality assurance schemes in all Member States** to support the promotion of bio-waste derived fertilisers while ensuring safety and functionality.

Main takeaways

To accelerate the transition toward a circular economy, HOOP advocates for a robust and coherent policy framework that empowers Member States and regions to act decisively and innovatively. More specifically, authors suggest:

✓ Revising key regulations and regulatory frameworks: 767/2009 (Annex III Chapter 1.6) and 1069/2009 (Art. 5) and the Industrial Emission Directive 2010/75/EU, the Invasive Alien Species Regulation to unlock the potential of emerging bioproducts like insect feed and biochar; streamlining the establishment of EU-wide End-of-Waste criteria, product categories for biowaste-derived materials and setting a dedicated regulatory framework for biotechnology.

✓ Promoting innovation and investment, by expanding funding for innovation procurement (pre-commercial public procurement and public procurement of innovation) and by ensuring that the EU Taxonomy allows flexibility for high-performing, innovative technologies not explicitly listed. Additionally, Member States need technical and financial support to navigate complex compliance procedures, particularly in collaboration with EFSA and DG SANTE.

By implementing these policy recommendations, the EU can lead the way in sustainable biowaste management, fostering innovation, protecting the environment, and creating new economic opportunities across its Member States.

Looking for a graphical, concise yet informative resume of the project concept and results? Check out the [HOOP booklet "Closing the HOOP: A legacy of circular innovation"](#)

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